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A Degradable and Antimicrobial Surface-attached Polymer Hydrogel^a

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Keywords

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Abstract

Surface-attached, degradable polymer hydrogels with potential antimicrobial activity are reported. They were obtained by ring-opening metathesis copolymerization (ROMP) of a monomer with potential bioactivity and a monomer that carries a benzophenone cross-linker and a hydrolyzable group. The hydrolyzable group was either an ester or an anhydride group. The copolymers thus obtained were spin-coated onto silicon wafers and UV-irradiated to induce C,H cross-linking of the benzophenone groups and obtain the target polymer networks. Immersion of these networks into aqueous media triggered network degradation. The degradation speed depended on the nature of the intended break points (ester or anhydride groups), the number of cross-links per polymer chain, and the surrounding medium. By releasing bioactive polymer fragments to the medium ("leaching") and by regenerating the hydrogel surface during the degradation process, the hydrogels potentially have two ways to prevent biofilm formation on their surface.

FIGURE FOR ToC_ABSTRACT

1. Introduction

The world-wide increase of antimicrobial resistance of bacteria is alarming.^[1] In this context, it is particularly worrying that the infection of medical devices and implants in consequence of bacterial biofilm formation is still an unresolved issue.¹⁻³ To reduce biofilm formation, a number of contact-active, antimicrobial polymer coatings has been reported.^[2-4] In vitro, they work reliably and destroy bacteria near-quantitatively.^[2-7] However, since contact-active antimicrobial coatings are positively charged, the

debris of destroyed bacteria and other biomolecules tend to adhere to such surfaces. Thus, if they are applied in an open system, incoming bacteria will settle on these contaminations and colonize the surface. In other words, if contact-active, cationic antimicrobial polymer coatings are used in areas with continuous influx of pathogens, biofilm formation will be retarded but not ultimately prevented. Alternative solutions that slow down biofilm formation are polymer coatings that leach antimicrobials,^[2, 3] or materials that can throw off their top layer once contaminated, like a reptile shedding its skin.^[8] Recently, a number of dually active materials consisting of antimicrobial and protein-repellent components have also been reported,^[4, 9-13] as well as a polyzwitterion that has simultaneous antimicrobial activity and protein-repellency.^[14] Since there is no "one size fits all" solution for the diverse areas where biofilm prevention is required, each of these strategies has its merits, and will probably lead to complementary solutions for different applications. However, since many of these approaches require complicated materials syntheses and/or multi-step surface modifications, a simple, straightforward approach to obtain a degradable contact-active antimicrobial polymer coating would be desirable. Hedrick pioneered this area with the development of degradable polycarbonates,^[15, 16] and antimicrobial polyesters with main-chain degradability have also been developed.^[17, 18] Other materials with potential antimicrobial and surface-regenerating properties due to degradation or depolymerization have also been reported.^[19-21] These were based, for example, on the degradation of the linker between an antimicrobial fragment and a carrier polymer,^[19] depolymerization of a self-immolative polymer,^[21] and the degradation of a so-called polyactive material (i.e. a polymer containing an antimicrobial pro-drug that releases the active drug by degradation).^[20]

We here present an antimicrobial poly(oxanorbornene)-based hydrogel that can be hydrolytically degraded. As it turned out to be notoriously difficult to include degradable groups into the poly(oxanorbornene) main chain, we chose a different approach to obtain the desired material. The target material consists of an antimicrobial poly(oxanorbornene)^[7, 22, 23] with not too high molecular weight, which carries additional side chains with a degradable unit (**X**) and a functional group (**Y**) (Figure 1) next to each other. The functional group **Y** is used to connect the antimicrobial polymer chains to a hydrogel,

while **X** ensures its degradability upon exposure to aqueous conditions. Thus, hydrolysis of **X** triggers degradation of the polymer network, and potentially antimicrobial polymer fragments are released into the surroundings of the antimicrobial coating. These fragments are small enough not to form microplastics particles (and thus do not permanently contaminate the environment), but should have the right molecular weight to interact with planktonic bacteria and reduce their growth rate.^[23] Thus, the obtained material could be dually active through simultaneous surface-activity and leaching of active components. In order to obtain such a system, the reactivities of **X** and **Y** need to be orthogonal. In our system, **X** is either an ester group or an anhydride, which can be hydrolyzed in water. **Y** is a benzophenone group, which can undergo C,H insertion cross-linking when UV-irradiated.^[24] The group **Y** is used to form a covalent cross-link (black dots in Figure 1) to neighboring chains, so that a polymer hydrogel can be obtained upon UV irradiation. Likewise, a substrate carrying **Y** is used, so that the hydrogel becomes surface-attached. We here report the synthesis of two monomers, **M1** and **M2**, with different **X** groups, and their copolymerization by ring-opening metathesis polymerization (ROMP) with the precursor monomer **M3** which, after activation, would render the final polymer hydrogel antimicrobially active. We then investigate the degradation of the polymer hydrogels obtained.

Figure 1. Material Design. a) First, a copolymer consisting of potentially antimicrobial repeat units and a small fraction of repeat units with degradable (**X**) and cross-linker groups (**Y**) is synthesized. b) Upon UV-irradiation, the cross-linkers form a surface attached hydrogel by C,H-insertion reactions. c) Under aqueous conditions, the network degrades at **X** and thereby renews its surface. It also releases fragments with potential bioactivity.

2. Experimental Section

General information on chemicals, instrumentation and measurement conditions is given in the supporting information. All manipulations were performed under nitrogen atmosphere.

Synthesis of 4-benzoylbenzoic acid chloride (R1). 5.00 g (24.9 mmol, 1 eq.) 4-benzoylbenzoic acid was dissolved in 29.6 g (249 mmol, 10 eq.) thionyl chloride and refluxed for 3 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled down, and the unreacted thionyl chloride was removed using a rotary evaporator. To remove further traces of SOCl_2 , the product obtained was re-dissolved in dry toluene twice, and each time the added solvent was removed using a rotary evaporator. The product was obtained in near-quantitative yields as a colorless powder, which was taken to the next reaction step without further purification.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (250 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) = 8.24 (m, 2H, CH_{AR}), 7.85 (m, 4H, CH_{AR}), 7.66 (m, 1H, CH_{AR}), 7.53 (m, 2H, CH_{AR}).

Synthesis of N-(2-(4-benzoylbenzoic acid)-ethyl)-5-norbornene-2,3-dicarboxylic acid imide (M1). 5.00 g (20.4 mmol, 1 eq.) 4-benzoylbenzoic acid chloride **R1** and N-(2-hydroxyethyl)-5-norbornene-2,3-dicarboxylic acid imide 4.27 g (20.4 mmol, 1 eq.) were dissolved in dichloromethane. The mixture was cooled to 0°C using ice, and 5.17 g (51.0 mmol, 2.5 eq) triethylamine were added drop by drop while the reaction temperature was not allowed to increase. After stirring over night, the reaction mixture was washed with aqueous KHSO_4 (10%) and water twice, and dried using sodium sulfate. After removal of the drying agent by filtration, the solvent was removed using a rotary evaporator, which yielded the pure product.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (250 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) = 8.06-8.17 (m, 2H, CH_{AR}), 7.76-7.89 (m, 4H, CH_{AR}), 7.58-7.69 (m, 1H, CH_{AR}), 7.45-7.56 (m, 2H, CH_{AR}), 6.51 (s, 2H, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$), 5.25 (s, 2H, CH-O-CH), 4.50 (t, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 3.94 (t, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{-N}$), 2.89 (s, 2H, $\text{CH-C}=\text{O}$). $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (62.9 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) = 196.0 ($\text{C}_{\text{AR}}\text{-C}(\text{=O})\text{-C}_{\text{AR}}$), 176.0 ($\text{C}(\text{=O})\text{-N}$), 165.5 ($\text{C}(\text{=O})\text{O}$), 136.5 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$), 128.4-141.4 (C_{AR}), 80.9 (C-O-C), 61.7 ($\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 47.5 ($\text{CH}_2\text{-N}$), 37.8 ($\text{C-C}(\text{=O})\text{N}$).

Synthesis of exo-5-norbornenecarboxylic acid (4-benzoylbenzoic acid) anhydride (M2). 420 mg (3 mmol, 1 eq.) 4-benzoylbenzoic acid chloride **R1** was dissolved in dry dichloromethane. The mixture was

cooled to 0°C using an ice bath, and 2.86 g (36.2 mmol, 1 eq.) dry pyridine was slowly added. Next, 8.87 g (36.2 mmol, 1 eq.) exo-5-norbornenecarboxylic acid was added, and the ice bath was removed. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 2 hours and cooled down. The colorless precipitate was removed by filtration, and washed with ice-cold dry dichloromethane. The solution was then put into the freezer, so that more product was obtained. This product was also isolated by filtration, and washed. Care was taken to perform these manipulations speedily to avoid hydrolysis of the anhydride by humidity.

¹H-NMR (250 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 8.26 (m, 2H, CH_{AR}), 7.85 (m, 4H, CH_{AR}), 7.66 (m, 1H, CH_{AR}), 7.53 (m, 2H, CH_{AR}), 6.15 (m, 2H, CH=CH), 3.17 & 2.98 (m, 2H, CH-CH₂-CH), 2.35 & 2.00 (m, 2H, CH-CH₂-CH), 1.48 (m, 3H, CH-C(=O) & CH₂-CH-(C=O)). ¹³C-NMR (62.9 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 195.56 (C_{AR}-C(=O)-C_{AR}), 176.14 (C(=O)), 161.35 (C(=O)), 138.46 & 135.34 (C=C), 128.48-142.90 (C_{AR}), 46.36(C_{Br}), 44.39 (C_{Br}-C), 42.95 (C-C=O), 41.68 (C_{Br}-C), 30.35 (CH₂).

Synthesis of Copolymers P1 and P2. The reagent amounts for the synthesis of the copolymers are given in Table 2. The two monomers were dissolved in dichloromethane, so that the total monomer concentration was about 0.1 g/mL. Grubbs catalyst G3 was dissolved in 100 μL dry dichloromethane. The monomer mixture was added to the catalyst solution in one shot, and the reaction was stirred at room temperature for 30 min. The reaction was quenched by adding excess (about 1 mL) of ethylvinyl ether. After a 30 min, the solvent and excess ethylvinyl ether was removed using a rotary evaporator, and the dry product was taken up in a small amount of dichloromethane. It was precipitated into cold hexane and recovered by filtration. This was repeated until the polymer was almost colorless. The polymer was then dried under high vacuum. An ¹H-NMR spectrum of a polymer thus obtained (**P1-10%**) is shown in the supporting information (Figure S3). The molecular weight M_n of all polymers were determined by gel permeation chromatography and are included in Table 1.

Synthesis and Degradation of Surface-attached Polymer Hydrogels. To obtain the hydrogels, the **P1** or **P2** polymer was dissolved in dry dichloromethane at a concentration of 25 mg mL⁻¹. This solution was then spin-coated at 3000 rpm onto 3EBP-functionalized^[7] silicon wafers pieces (1.5 x 1.5 cm²). The thus

coated substrates were crosslinked by UV irradiation (254 nm, 30 min). They were then washed with dry dichloromethane to remove unbound polymer chains, and dried under nitrogen flow. For degradation, they were immersed into stirred solutions (3 M aqueous HCl or PBS buffer, respectively). At the designated time points, one wafer piece was removed, washed with distilled water, and dried quickly under nitrogen flow. The thickness at $t = 0$ and the designated degradation time points was determined by ellipsometry (Table S1).

3. Results

Material Design. To obtain the above described poly(oxanorbornenes)-based, degradable surface-attached polymer hydrogels, we first needed trifunctional norbornene monomers that carried the functional units **X** and **Y** in addition to a polymerizable norbornene derivative. These monomers needed to be designed in such a way that their polymerization with the bioactive comonomer, the hydrogel formation and the hydrogel degradation step occur by mutually orthogonal reactions. This was possible since norbornene derivatives are polymerized by ring-opening metathesis polymerization (ROMP),^[25] which is catalyzed by highly specific initiators only. We chose benzophenone as group **Y** since it can undergo UV-triggered C,H-insertion cross-linking to form the hydrogel, but is not affected by aqueous hydrolysis reactions. For **X**, we needed a functional group that can undergo hydrolysis, preferentially under physiological conditions. For this, an ester group and an anhydride group were chosen. Poly(esters) degrade under physiological conditions, yet slowly, while the degradation rates of poly(anhydrides) is several orders of magnitude higher.^[26] Since neither the poly(norbornene) nor the C-C bond formed by the benzophenone group are sensitive to hydrolysis, this choice of **X** made sure that degradation by hydrolysis will happen exclusively at **X**.

Polymer Synthesis. The chemical structure and synthesis of the target monomers **M1** and **M2** containing **X** and **Y** is shown in Scheme 1. First, commercially available 4-benzylbenzoic acid was reacted with thionyl chloride under reflux to give 4-benzoylbenzoic acid chloride **R1** in near-quantitative yields. After

removal of the excess thionyl chloride under vacuum, **R1** could be used without further purification. The oxanorbornene derivative **R2** was then dissolved in dichloromethane and reacted with **R1** under typical acid chloride esterification conditions (0°C, 2.5 eq triethyl amine). After washing with KHSO₄ and solvent removal, the pure product **M1** was obtained. **R1** was also the starting material for the synthesis of the anhydride monomer **M2**. To obtain this monomer, the norbornene derivative **R3** was dissolved in THF and cooled to 0°C. 1 eq of pyridine was added, followed by slow addition of **R1** dissolved in THF. The mixture was brought to room temperature and refluxed. The precipitated product **M2** was recovered by filtration. Thus, the two monomers could be obtained in simple synthetic steps and without excessive work-up. The ¹H-NMR spectra of **M1** and **M2** are shown in Figures S1 and S2 of the supporting information.

Scheme 1: Synthesis of monomers with intended break points. **M1** and **M2** were obtained from benzoylbenzoic acid and carry an ester or an anhydride group as **X**, respectively.

The monomers **M1** and **M2** were each copolymerized with the oxanorbornene monomer **M3**, which as previously reported would impart bioactivity to the resulting materials (Scheme 2).^[7, 22, 27] **M3** was synthesized as reported previously.^[27] To obtain the target polymers **P1** and **P2**, the monomers **M1** and **M3** (or **M2** and **M3**, respectively) were mixed at the desired ratios (Table 1), so that polymers with 2.5, 5 and 10 mol% benzophenone-carrying repeat units would be obtained. The target molecular weights of the

polymers are also given in Table 1. (Therein, the polymers are labeled by their content of repeat units carrying benzophenone groups. E.g. **P1-2.5%** refers to the copolymer obtained from 2.5 mol% **M1** and 97.5 mol% **M3**.) Grubbs third generation catalyst was added to initiate the ring-opening metathesis polymerization (ROMP) of the monomer pairs **M1/M3** and **M2/M3** at room temperature, giving the usual quantitative monomer conversion observed for such monomer-catalyst systems. The reactive chain end was quenched by addition of ethyl vinyl ether, and the polymers were recovered by precipitation. They were then characterized by ¹H-NMR spectroscopy (see Figure S3 for the spectrum of polymer **P1-10%** as an example) and gel permeation chromatography (GPC). All ¹H-NMR spectra showed the peak broadening characteristic for polymers. To check that the desired ratio of repeat units was obtained, the peaks of the propyl group at 0.89 ppm and the benzophenone group between 7.5 and 8.3 ppm were compared. The results showed that the ratio of benzophenone to propyl-oxanorbornene repeat units matched the ratio of the monomer input (**M1** to **M3**, or **M2** to **M3**, respectively). The GPC data obtained for the copolymer series **P1** and **P2** are summarized in Table 1, and a typical elugram for each polymer type is shown in Figure 2.

Table 1: Reagent amounts and GPC data for polymer series **P1** to **P2** (in CHCl₃, SDV column, PMMA standards).

Copolymer	M1 or M2 m [mg]	M3 m [mg]	G3 m [mg]	$M_{n, target}$ [g mol ⁻¹]	$M_{n, GPC}$ [g mol ⁻¹]	PDI
P1-2.5%	15	450	8.8	38,400	39,000	1.1
P1-5%	28	450	8.8	39,400	41,000	1.1
P1-10%	113	900	19.6	37,500	39,000	1.1
P2-2.5%	6	200	4.3	34,800	39,000	1.3
P2-5%	11	200	4.3	35,600	41,000	1.6
P2-10%	21	200	4.3	37,300	42,000	1.9

Scheme 2: Polymers **P1** and **P2** were obtained by ring-opening metathesis copolymerization (ROMP) of **M1** + **M3**, or **M2** + **M3** respectively, initiated by Grubbs 3rd generation catalyst G3.

Figure 2. GPC elugram of **P1-2.5%** and **P2-2.5%**, respectively (in CHCl_3 , SDV column, PMMA standards).

This data show that the GPC results of the **P1** polymers were in good agreement with targeted molecular weights, and that all **P1** polymers had the low polydispersity typical for ROMP products. For the **P2** polymers, on the other hand, the observed molecular weights were higher, and a shoulder on the high molecular weight flank of the GPC elugram was observed (shown for **P2-2.5%** in Figure 2). Thus, an increased polydispersity compared to the corresponding ester polymers **P1** was observed. This effect shown for **P2-2.5%** in Figure 2 is even enhanced for the polymers of the **P2** series with higher anhydride content. Since ROMP reactions are not normally prone to termination by cross-linking, the additional higher molecular weight peak is most likely the result of a reaction of the highly active anhydride group with the N-H proton of the Boc group. The polymers obtained by this side reaction have double the molecular weight of the target polymers, and even a small percentage of this can thus lead to the observed shoulder in the GPC elugram, and the observed shift of the measured molecular weight compared to the targeted one. Fortunately, this reaction was so slow under the given conditions that no polymer gelation occurred.

Surface-attached Polymer Hydrogels. The different versions of **P1** and **P2** were each dissolved in chloroform and spin-coated onto silicon wafer pieces that had been functionalized with triethoxy 3-(4-benzoylphenoxy) silane (**3EBP**) as reported previously.^[7] The polymer films thus obtained were UV irradiated at a wavelength of 254 nm, and then washed with chloroform to remove unbound polymer chains. The thickness of these polymer films was determined by ellipsometry, and was between 85 and 100 nm (Table S1). Thus, solvent-stable surface-attached polymer networks were obtained. A typical FTIR spectrum of such a network is shown in the supporting information (Figure S4, FTIR-Spectrum of **P2-10%**). Both the signals caused by the C-H stretching vibrations of the aromatic protons (just below 3000 cm⁻¹) and the anhydride signals (around 1720 cm⁻¹) are clearly visible in that spectrum. To study the degradation of the polymer hydrogels, eight identically coated wafer pieces were immersed into 3 M HCl or PBS buffer, respectively, and removed from these solutions after 1, 2, 4, 8, 24, 48 or 168 hours. They were then dried, and the dry layer thickness for each time point was also determined by ellipsometry. The data thus obtained is summarized in Table S1. In Figure 3, this data is plotted as normalized layer

thickness ($= \text{thickness at time } t / \text{thickness at } t = 0$) versus time t . For the **P1** series with the ester groups as intended break points, the layer thickness of the samples was reduced to 54-66% of the original layer thickness within 168 h in HCl, depending on the amount of ester cross-links (Figure 3a). Notably, the thickness loss was highest for the samples with 2.5% ester groups, and lowest for the samples with 10% ester groups. This matches the expected trend that more cross-links lead to slower hydrogel degradation. Judging from the slope of the curve, the degradation in HCl was not completed within the timeframe investigated, as no plateau was yet reached. For these polymer coatings, degradation in PBS was not studied because it would be an extremely slow process. The same qualitative trend respecting the dependency of degradation speed on crosslinker content was found for the different members of the polymer series **P2** when degraded in HCl (Figure 3b). Only this time, the thickness was reduced to 9.4% - 21% of the original sample thickness within the same time span. This is plausible, since the anhydride linkers contained in these polymer hydrogels hydrolyze faster than the corresponding esters. Interestingly, the degradation of these materials seemed to level off into a plateau between 24 and 48 h for all samples observed, and the materials only degraded further at much longer times. This could be related to the above mentioned side reactions between the anhydride and the carbamate, which led to additional cross-links in the network. These cross-links are chemically different to the anhydride groups and hydrolyze after longer reaction times. The degradation of **P2-2.5%** was also studied by FTIR, as shown in Figures S4 and S5 of the supporting information. The results indicate a continuous intensity reduction of the anhydride adsorption band at 1717 cm^{-1} (Figure S5), which however does not completely vanish even after 168 h. This is in agreement with the ellipsometry data, which showed a remainder of polymer on the wafer after 168 h, which was however thicker than the thickness of a surface-attached monolayer. When the polymers of the **P2** series were degraded in PBS, expectedly their degradation rate was slower than in HCl. Under these degradation conditions, the process stopped at a value specific for each cross-linker content (38-69%, respectively) after about 48 h. This plateau could also be related to the above mentioned side reaction. The additional cross-links formed by acetylation of the carbamate would not hydrolyze at pH 7.4 and thus could prevent full cleavage of the polymer hydrogels.

Figure 3. Degradation kinetics of the surface-attached polymer hydrogels. Normalized layer thickness is plotted versus time. a) **P1** in HCl, b) **P2** in HCl, c) **P2** in PBS buffer.

To get a visual impression of the degradation process, atomic force microscopy images of **P2-5%** degraded in PBS were taken at 0 h, 4 h, 24 h, and 168 h, respectively (Figure 4). The series of images shows that the initially smooth surfaces (with some point defects formed during spin-coating) become increasingly inhomogeneous, and that a crater-like morphology was obtained after 168 h. Thus, material remained on the surface even after 168 hours, which is in good agreement with the ellipsometry and FTIR data.

Figure 4. Degradation of **P2-5%** in PBS buffer, studied by atomic force microscopy at different time points.

As is well known, polymers can either degrade by surface erosion or bulk erosion, where the exact mechanism depends on the water permeability of the material.^[28] For samples thicker than the so-called

critical length, surface erosion takes place at the interface of the material and the surrounding medium up to a material depth corresponding to the critical length, while the bulk of the material remains unaffected. For samples thinner than the critical length, bulk erosion occurs, i.e. hydrolysis of degradable bonds is observed throughout the sample.^[28] The critical length is about 75 μm for polyanhydrides, and 1.3 cm for the polyester poly(ϵ -caprolactone).^[28] Both values are orders of magnitude above the sample thickness here investigated (100 nm). We therefore assume bulk erosion. However, it is not possible to conclude this (or the opposite) from the data here presented. As recently shown by Ruhe and coworkers,^[29] degradation of surface-attached polymer networks can be explained by percolation theory. Thus, what we see is probably not the gradual release of material from the surface of the film, but the gradual release of larger fragments that eventually become disconnected from the material. This interpretation would be in agreement with the AFM images, which demonstrate increasing surface roughness and the formation of small holes in the material.

For the intended purpose of these materials - i.e. antimicrobial surfaces that can continuously remove bacterial debris by erosion - in practice the degradation results mean that the **P2** hydrogels renew their surface in physiological medium within the first two days only. In that time frame, polymer chains would be released and could combat planktonic bacteria near the surface, while bacteria that adhere to the surface would be simultaneously shed. This could already slow down biofilm formation within the first two days of use. For such a system to be truly effective for longer times, the undesired side reactions between the cross-linkers and the functional groups on the antimicrobial moiety need to be avoided. This is far from trivial and requires a re-design of the antimicrobial moieties. For the **P1** polymers, however, a continuous mass loss is observed within 168 h, so that these materials could potentially regenerate their surface for at least 7 days.

Patten and coworkers recently demonstrated the release of antimicrobial aldehydes that were incorporated into degradable polyactive acetals through their diallyl acetal analogues.^[20] Although the study of these polyactives focused on drug release and not on surface morphology or the degradation of the material

itself, one can assume that such surfaces could also be simultaneously antimicrobial and surface-regenerating. However, the surface of these materials is probably not antimicrobially active since the precursor polymer is not. This may or may not be a problem for practical applications, depending on the drug release and bulk material degradation rates. The self-immolative antimicrobial polymers presented by Palermo provide another highly interesting platform to obtain materials that are simultaneously antimicrobial and self-regenerating.^[21] These polymers are above their ceiling temperature and do not depolymerize because they are end-capped and thus "trapped" in a metastable state. When exposed to a chemical trigger that hydrolyzes the end-cap, they depolymerized and thereby release antimicrobial fragments.^[21] Thus, these surfaces are also simultaneously antimicrobially active at the surface and release antimicrobial fragments. As a coating, they could thus also remove potential biofilm fragments from the surface and thus fulfil a similar purpose as the material we were aiming at in this publication. Once these materials can be cleaved with a physiologically relevant trigger, and the depolymerization rates (which are quite fast at the moment) can be controlled to useful drug release rates combined with the required surface regeneration rates, they could thus also be useful materials from a surface regeneration perspective. The coincidence of these two papers and this publication within less than a year indicate that the surface regeneration aspect is deemed increasingly important by the scientific community.

Conclusion.

We here presented the synthesis and polymerization of two (oxa)norborene derivatives that each carried a benzophenone cross-linker group, and an ester or anhydride linker as an intended break point. These two monomers could be smoothly copolymerized with potentially bioactive monomers by ring-opening metathesis polymerization (ROMP). From the polymers thus synthesized, surface-attached hydrogels were obtained by UV irradiation. When immersed into aqueous media, these materials would degrade and thereby release small, potentially bioactive polymer layer fragments to the surrounding medium. At the same time, their surface is regenerated by degradation. The degradation rate depended both on the nature of the cross-linker, the cross-linker content, and the pH of the surrounding medium. While the physical

properties that could give rise to the postulated dual mechanism of antimicrobial activity have been demonstrated, this dual activity itself was not yet shown because of undesired side reactions in one the here presented systems. However, ongoing work is dedicated such a system with dual antimicrobial activity in a single component without the undesired side reactions with the bioactive groups.

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